

The HuT

Guidelines on climate-proofing planning

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T3.1 Enablers and barriers to multi-hazard/systemic risk reduction

AUTHORS

Luz Adriana Gomez-Mogollon (CMCC), Alfredo Reder (CMCC), Guido Rianna (CMCC),
Kristina Viršilaitė (CMCC)

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Project Coordinator	Michele Calvello UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI SALERNO mcalvello@unisa.it
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3. Purpose

Task 3.1 has the goal of identifying and addressing the governance/policy/financing enablers and barriers for implementing innovative and integrated multi-hazard systemic risk reduction strategies based on experience in the demonstrators. It has three main pillars:

- Examine the institutional/procedural and financial reforms necessary for a wide-scale implementation of nature-based solutions.
- Climate-proofing design and planning: support the reform of local standards and governance strategies such that they account for weather forcing under climate change.
- Suggest reforms of selected governance strategies to better manage multi-risk (cascading/compound events)

In coherence with the second pillar, *Deliverable 3.2: Guidelines on Climate-proofing planning* describes a proposed framework to support the incorporation of climate change effects into the design of urban infrastructure, as well as its implementation in two different DEMs. In each of the two DEMs, an urban context was identified in which, as a use case, the need for an upgrade of the urban drainage network for stormwater management is considered. The framework is illustrated for urban drainage systems, but it is expected to be applicable to other urban structures as well. Similarly, the approach is fully transferable to other geographical contexts.

At the beginning of this document, key aspects regarding the climate-proofing planning process in European societies and economies are discussed. Then, the proposed framework is described step-by-step, aiming to facilitate its application and interpretation by local designers and planners. Subsequently, the testing of the framework for urban drainage systems in the old town of Vilnius city (Demonstrator 4) and a strategic area in Naples city (near Demonstrator 3) is described. Finally, some recommendations and limitations to be considered in subsequent replications of the framework are presented.

4. Climate-proofing planning

Climate change is transforming European societies and economies. For some types of extreme weather events, more significantly driven by atmospheric warming, statistically relevant increases are already occurring in terms of frequency and/or with greater severity, exerting unprecedented pressure on ecosystems, populations, and infrastructure. Catastrophic floods in central Europe devastating wildfires in the Mediterranean, and prolonged droughts across large parts of the continent have resulted in human losses, disrupted supply chains, and caused significant economic costs (Copernicus Climate Change Service & World Meteorological Organization, 2025). In 2022, heatwaves alone were responsible for more than 60,000 premature deaths in Europe, while annual damages from extreme climate events already exceeded €12 billion (EEA, 2024).

These impacts emphasize that climate change acts as a risk multiplier. It worsens existing vulnerabilities in the built environment, agriculture, water management, energy, and health systems, while causing cascading effects that cross sectors and borders. A flood can trigger disruptions in energy supplies, affect transportation networks, destabilize financial markets, and increase social inequalities. The systemic nature of climate risks means that adaptation and resilience efforts are not optional as they are essential for protecting lives, economies, and long-term sustainability (EEA, 2024).

Various scientific studies and institutional reports have clearly shown that it is economically unfeasible to address increased costs solely through response measures; instead, prevention and preparedness actions are necessary. Anticipatory actions, in overall terms, have often proven more effective. One of the main guiding principles in prevention is to explicitly consider, during the design or retrofitting of new infrastructure, the potential burdens associated with climate change. This approach is commonly referred to as climate proofing. Exploiting the work carried by Commission Notice “Technical guidance on the climate proofing of infrastructure in the period 2021-2027” [C(2021) 5430 final], “Climate proofing is a process that integrates climate change mitigation and adaptation measures into the development of infrastructure projects. It enables European institutional and private investors to make informed decisions on projects that qualify as compatible with the Paris Agreement.”

Climate proofing involves making investments, policies, and projects resilient to both current and future climate conditions. It ensures infrastructure and assets remain operational and effective throughout their lifespan, even in the face of climate extremes. Climate proofing covers both mitigation (cutting greenhouse gas emissions) and adaptation (boosting resilience to unavoidable impacts), and it aims to avoid maladaptation, i.e., investments that unintentionally increase vulnerability or trap societies in high-risk pathways (European Commission, 2021a).

At its core, climate proofing provides three key benefits:

1. Reducing exposure and vulnerability by incorporating risk assessments and climate projections into planning and design.
2. Enhancing resilience through robust, adaptable, and nature-based solutions capable of withstanding climate extremes.
3. Ensuring compliance with EU policy and funding requirements, thus enabling access to climate-aligned investment opportunities.

The European Commission has emphasized the importance of climate proofing in its *Technical Guidance on the Climate Proofing of Infrastructure in the Period 2021–2027* (European Commission, 2021a). This guidance provides a practical framework for incorporating climate

adaptation and mitigation considerations into infrastructure projects funded by the EU. It requires project developers to evaluate climate risks, identify adaptation measures, and ensure that design standards consider future climate conditions.

The need for climate-proofing is strengthened by the Do No Significant Harm (DNSH) principle, embedded in the EU Taxonomy Regulation (European Commission, 2020). The DNSH principle states that investments supporting one environmental goal (e.g., climate change mitigation) must not cause significant harm to others (e.g., adaptation, water resources, biodiversity). For infrastructure, this means that projects should account for resilience to climate change impacts and prevent locking in future vulnerabilities.

By linking climate proofing with DNSH, the EU guarantees that financed projects provide co-benefits across environmental, social, and economic spheres. For instance, a flood protection system must not only diminish immediate risk but also support ecosystem preservation, sustainable land use, and long-term climate adaptation strategies.

Together, the DNSH principle and the Technical Guidance create a comprehensive framework for integrating climate resilience into Europe's investment cycle. They align with the *European Green Deal, the EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change* (European Commission, 2021b), and the legally binding goal of climate neutrality by 2050 under the European Climate Law (European Parliament & Council, 2021).

The built environment plays a key role in climate resilience efforts, as it is highly exposed to climate hazards and essential for societal functions. Buildings, energy networks, transport infrastructure, and water systems are susceptible to floods, heatwaves, and storms, and disruptions to these can have ripple effects on economies and communities. Built environments must be resilient and adapt to potential climate variations to minimize negative impacts on human life and built systems. It is fundamental that the infrastructure planning process ensures “build back better” for those needing to be rebuilt and a proper retrofit to accommodate those yet working but designed accounting for “steady” weather forcing. The Joint Research Centre emphasizes that adapting the built environment involves updating design standards (such as the second-generation Eurocodes), harmonizing climate data, and incorporating future climate scenarios into structural assessments.

Urban areas are of particular concern. They concentrate populations, assets, and economic activities, while also amplifying climate hazards through the urban heat island effect and extensive soil sealing. Cities must therefore prioritize sustainable urban drainage systems (SUDS), blue-green infrastructure, and nature-based solutions that manage stormwater, reduce heat stress, and enhance biodiversity. These measures provide multiple benefits: they increase resilience, contribute to mitigation by storing carbon, and support the DNSH principle by improving rather than degrading ecosystem services.

While climate proofing is often discussed as a technical task, its success relies on governance and societal participation. Effective climate proofing requires:

- Multi-level coordination, from EU institutions to national governments, municipalities, and private actors.
- Integration across policy sectors, including climate, energy, transport, health, finance, and social cohesion.
- Consideration of equity and justice, ensuring that adaptation measures do not unfairly burden vulnerable groups.
- Capacity-building and knowledge sharing, especially within local administrations and design communities.

In any case, societal preparedness remains low, and the gap between climate risk levels and policy implementation is widening (EEA, 2024). Closing this gap requires urgent, coordinated action, with climate proofing as a central guiding principle.

This document places climate proofing within European and global adaptation discussions while providing a framework for its practical use. By integrating scientific evidence, policy advice, and case studies, it aims to support the development and realization of climate-proof planning strategies. Particular focus is given to urban drainage systems, where climate hazards like pluvial flooding directly relate to infrastructure design, land use, and community resilience. Ultimately, climate proofing is not merely a technical requirement or policy duty; it is a societal promise. It ensures that Europe's investments foster a resilient, sustainable, and fair future, in line with the DNSH principle, the EU Adaptation Strategy, and the long-term goal of climate neutrality.

5. Framework for climate-proofing planning

Incorporating potential climate change impacts into the planning process of structure/infrastructure is imperative in order to minimize negative impacts on human life and built systems. However, each project, each community, has its own specific needs, vulnerabilities, and capacities and limitations to adapt that must be taken into account during the process. Besides, the inherent uncertainty of climate change projections has to be handled in a particular way that may also depend on local specificities. Therefore, *the Framework for climate-proofing planning* described and applied here aims to be a support in the process, highlighting the most relevant aspects to be considered.

As a first step in the climate-proofing process, it is required to perform a climate change risk assessment to identify whether and how projected changes in climate variables could significantly impact the system at hand. Based on this assessment, decisions can be made regarding system design, reinforcement, improvement, or re-design. It is worth mentioning that this assessment should be made as early as possible in the planning process.

Traditionally, climate change risk assessment is implemented through a methodological approach known as top-down. This approach has as its starting point the outcomes of climate simulations, either from global or regional climate models, under several future scenarios. Then, changes in local climate or systems are analyzed in terms of potential impacts under specific scenarios. This flow is illustrated in Figure 1 for a water system. It is highlighted that the uncertainty through this approach tends to propagate and add up, leading to an overwhelmingly large range of potential results, making the decision-making process difficult (Fowler et al., 2024; Pfliederer et al., 2025).

Figure 1. Schematic of the typical top-down approach. Modified from Fowler et al., (2024)

Although the top-down approach seems straightforward from a climate scientist perspective, for stakeholder groups it can appear technocratic and “science-led” (Fowler et al., 2024). This perception is mostly due to the lack of relevance given to the local context within the approach. That is why, currently, reverse approaches known as bottom-up are fostered (Fowler et al., 2024; Pfliederer et al., 2025). The bottom-up approach focuses on understanding the system at hand and its unique vulnerabilities, usually from the inclusion of experience and knowledge of local stakeholders. This approach has as its principal aim to “translate” climate change projections, and the associated uncertainty, into useful information for the local context (IPCC, 2014; Koers et al., 2024; Ruane et al., 2022). It helps to bridge the gap between climate scientists, stakeholders, and experts on risk management (Koers et al., 2024).

The proposed climate-proofing planning framework is consistent with the bottom-up approach and highlights the importance of starting the analysis by identifying key climate indicators,

critical/problematic conditions, and adaptation limits of the system at hand. It is based on three known and widely used concepts:

- The Climatic Impact-Driver (CID) framework, adopted in the IPCC AR6 (IPCC, 2021), was designed to facilitate the contextualization of climate change impacts and the interaction between science and decision making. IPCC AR6 defined “climatic impact-drivers” (CIDs) as “*physical climate system conditions (e.g., means, events, extremes) that affect an element of society or ecosystems*”. Shifts in CIDs characteristics (intensity, frequency, duration, timing, spatial extent) can lead to positive, negative, or neutral outcomes depending on the context. Therefore, it is important to identify relevant CIDs for the system and the specific tolerance thresholds. These climatic thresholds can be natural, like heat conditions above which humans cannot regulate their internal temperatures, or structural, like engineered limits of a drainage system. Moreover, adaptation and risk management efforts can increase the resilience of the system by changing the threshold or modifying the climatic conditions that are considered problematic (IPCC, 2021; Ruane et al., 2022).
- A stress test is a special case of sensitivity analysis involving the analysis of the system under different combinations of stressors (aspects of a system that could change in the future) and with a particular interest in identifying combinations that lead to undesirable outcomes (Fowler et al., 2024).
- The Decision Scaling (DS) approach links information relevant for local decisions identified through bottom-up assessment with climate projections through a decision analysis framework (Brown et al., 2012; Brown et al., 2019). DS contemplate the characterization of the system through a model, a set of models, or empirical relationships that allow us to map the sensitivity of the system to a range of physically realistic climate conditions. This characterization is formalized through a sensitivity analysis, using variations on climate or non-climate factors of the system. Then, for the decision process, critical thresholds or climate conditions that have caused problems historically have to be identified. These values allow us to assess outcomes in terms of acceptable/unacceptable performance or decisions. Based on this, it is possible to identify vulnerabilities of the system linked to climate change from a perspective that is initially independent of a specific set of climate projections. Only at the final stage of the process, climate projections are considered and analyzed from a probabilistic perspective on how likely it is that future conditions fall into the unacceptable region or “failure zone”.

The following Sections present an overview of the framework and a clear description of the step-by-step procedure to follow for its implementation.

5.1. Framework overview

The framework, schematized on Figure 2, has as starting point *i*) the identification of main climate variables that can affect the system’s performance (e.g., precipitation and runoff for a water system, minimum and maximum temperature for a road, or wind and snow for a light building), *ii*) the definition of a feature and the related critical threshold associated with climate conditions that have caused problems in the past, and *iii*) a quantitative representation of the system that allows to link it with climate variables.

These initial elements are merged into a stress test that allows us to understand better *what conditions cause unacceptable results for the system*. Only after understanding the system and its relationship with climate variables, climate projections are incorporated into the analysis. The idea then is to estimate *the probability that the critical threshold is exceeded in the current period*

(used as baseline) and in the future accounting for the variations in climate forcing. Finally, if it is evident that some actions are required to make the system climate-proofed, it is necessary to identify which adaptation measures help to reduce the probability of exceeding the critical conditions.

Figure 2. Schematic of the implemented climate-proofing framework

To facilitate its implementation, the framework is structured into four steps (Figure 3). STEP 1 corresponds to the traditional design procedure, including, among other things, gathering information, defining model strategies, and establishing design parameters. STEP 2 involves understanding the local context (current infrastructure, local regulations, historical critical events, tolerance level) to determine the critical threshold of the system. At the end of STEP 2, the system is characterized, using a stress test, to establish the starting point or baseline conditions against which potential future variations will be evaluated. STEP 3 consists of using climate change projections to assess the likelihood of “unacceptable” outcomes in the future. STEP 4 is implemented when the results obtained at the end of STEP 3 indicate that the system is not climate-proofed (under established criteria), it involves the identification and assessment of potential adaptation measures.

During STEP 2 and 4, co-definition of the stages with the stakeholders is strongly encouraged to ensure that climate-proof planning exploits the local knowledge to identify the main vulnerabilities and the hidden adaptation capacity.

Figure 3. Main steps of the framework for climate-proofing planning

More detail on the step-by-step procedure is described in following Sections 5.2 to 5.5, and the concepts are illustrated for an urban drainage system (UDS) case.

5.2. STEP 1: System parameters

Gathering relevant information for the system design/planning

STEP 1 involves gathering information useful to characterize the system of interest, identifying frameworks to relate climate variables to system performance or parameters, and define the “current” baseline conditions. Among the most important aspects are: collecting information about the current infrastructure (e.g., physical aspects, known issues, planned interventions) and local construction regulations, and verifying the availability of hydrological/meteorological records and modeling strategies used for the design of current infrastructure.

Specifically, in the case of solutions to deal with urban flooding issues, STEP 1 addresses aspects such as:

- Collecting information about the current drainage network:
 - Type of drainage system: Stormwater Drainage or Combined Sewer System
 - Physical features: materials, diameters, slope and distribution of the pipes, manhole’s location.
 - Measurements: flow through the conduits and, in case of a combined system, the percentage of flow associated with wastewater.
- Retrieve spatial information about physical features, including digital elevation model and land use/land cover maps.
- Get forcing information, including precipitation records in the urban area of study and/or surrounding areas.
- Verify the availability of hydrological and/or hydraulic models of the current system.

Once the required information has been collected, it is expected to establish or to assess the existence of reference:

- Intensity-duration-frequency (IDF) curves to describe extreme events in the baseline period. In some cases, local regulations contain formulas to obtain IDF curves, the use of which should be assumed as baseline in design. However, if precipitation records are available, especially from recent decades, calculating or updating IDF curves is highly recommended to be sure that reference normative IDF do not result outdated due to the statistically significant trends that could affect the evolutions.
- Design storm duration and return period based on local regulations and drainage area characteristics.
- Rainfall-runoff modeling strategy to calculate the peak flow resulting from rainfall events
- Hydraulic modeling strategy to calculate the pipe dimensions required to ensure proper disposal of the surface runoff.

Regarding the rainfall-runoff and hydraulic models, their complexity is mostly going to depend on the available information and the specific characteristics of the system. Recent studies evaluate the impacts of climate change on the performance of urban stormwater systems, coupling climate model projections with models, like TOPMODEL, SWMM, DHI-MOUSE, and HEC-HMS (Hunu et al., 2024, Kourtis & Tsihrantzis, 2021). However, most of the models require precipitation and

streamflow information to calibrate their parameters, information that is not always available. Therefore, under conditions of scarce information, simplified approaches can be useful, like those based on conceptual models such as the Soil Conservation Service Curve Number (SCS-CN) method or the rational method (Yazdanfar & Sharma, 2015).

5.3. STEP 2: Critical threshold

Identifying the climate impact-driver (CID) and the “acceptable” frequency of occurrence

STEP 2 covers the understanding of the local context, starting from the definition of the critical threshold of the system. The critical threshold can be seen as the tolerance of the system to experience “failure” under the occurrence of fast or slow onset dynamics. It therefore constitutes the basis for assessing under what conditions the system can be considered climate-proof or needs to be “improved”/adapted (Brown et al., 2012; Pfliegerer et al., 2025).

The critical threshold is defined as the “acceptable” frequency of occurrence of a specific CID that is representative of climatic conditions that are considered problematic for the system. Identifying a critical threshold can be done on the basis of known natural or structural tolerance levels. Climate scientists and engineers can use expert judgment to take this decision. However, to have a meaningful threshold, it is recommended to include the local knowledge on how much risk is ‘tolerable’ (Pfliegerer et al., 2025; Ruane et al., 2022).

An optimal critical threshold definition integrates: i) characteristics and limits of the current system, ii) technical regulations; and iii) perception, expectation, and past learnings from as many stakeholders as possible (European Commission, 2021a; Haghghatafshar et. al., 2020). The latter element can be integrated through interactive sessions (workshops and focus groups) where stakeholders and communities can share local knowledge and past experiences and, in turn, be informed about potential impacts of climate change.

Once the CID is defined, a metric for its exceeding has to be assumed: for example, the frequency or the severity over the threshold; in the other hand, thresholds could be very different according to the specific interviewed stakeholders (it underlines the significance of properly characterizing the stakeholder landscape) while, under the same issue, in different socio-economic and geographical contexts entail very different thresholds. If an acceptable frequency of occurrence has to be specified, it can be coherent with the return period specified in local regulations. However, if stakeholders are involved and it is known that it can be acceptable that critical events occur with a higher average frequency, values other than the return period could be considered. Besides, it is also important to select the future horizon of interest based on, e.g., local planning strategies or regional adaptation plans.

At the end of this step, elements of STEP 1 and STEP 2 are used on a stress test to characterize the system (Brown et al., 2019; Fowler et al., 2024). It involves the variation of two or more system variables or *stressors*, which can be selected considering the importance of the variable to system outcomes and the sensitivity of the system to expected future changes (Fowler et al., 2024). The stress test can be made with two approaches: *i*) in terms of the system performance given variations on climate variables; or *ii*) in terms of decision optimization considering changes of non-climate factors (Brown et al., 2019).

The stress test is visualized on a multi-dimensional diagram that allows us to understand the climate effects on the system performance or how critical climate conditions vary due to changes in the system. The number of dimensions, usually associated with the number of stressors, depends on the complexity of the system. However, experience has shown that stakeholders are most receptive to two-dimensional visualizations (Brown et al., 2019). The space created due to the variation of stressors is called *performance space* when it is based on the system performance and *decision space* when it is based on the decision optimization, as shown in Figure 4.

Finally, the critical threshold is incorporated into the performance or decision space to split the outcomes into “acceptable” and “unacceptable” regions. It establishes the baseline conditions against which climate model projections will be evaluated (STEP 3) and constitutes an extremely powerful tool in the decision-making process.

Likewise, the performance of the current infrastructure can be assessed by checking whether the design under the reference climate conditions falls within the “acceptable” or “unacceptable” region.

Figure 4. Diagram of stress test results 2D visualization based on a simulation performance (left) and a decision optimization (right) approach.

For the urban flooding issues, an appropriated CID can be defined as a precipitation event with specific characteristics (frequency, intensity) associated with:

- the maximum peak flow that the drainage system can properly handle,
- historical flood events in critical areas of the city, or
- flood events with a specific depth and/or duration considered critical for the municipality.

Triggering conditions related to past flood events or the maximum UDS capacity can be obtained through an inverse modelling approach, as the one implemented by Cunderlik & Simonovic (2007), or from simple hydrologic-hydraulic relationships. The approach is going to depend on the available information and the modeling strategy selected in STEP 1.

In case of using a decision optimization approach for the stress test, it is recommended to select stressors that both influence the performance of the system and can be modified during the implementation of adaptation measures. In particular, three non-climate factors are highlighted for UDS: pipe dimensions, the percentage of rainfall that flows through the system, the effect of maintenance/aging on current pipe capacity.

5.4. STEP 3: Projections

Assessing the probability that the critical threshold could be significantly changed in the future

On STEP 3, the potential role of climate change on variations of weather variables is described quantitatively using a probabilistic framework based on the critical threshold and the regions of “acceptable” and “unacceptable” outcomes (Brown et al., 2019). It covers three main aspects: the selection of climate change projections, the mapping of projected values onto the stress test space, and the assessment of future probability of problematic conditions, i.e., when the critical threshold of the system is exceeded in the future.

The selection and processing of climate data have to take into account: i) the uncertainties about the modeling assumptions/parameterizations that lead to unique projections, for what it is recommended the use of an ensemble; ii) the uncertainties in the future societal development pathways, for which it is required to consider multiple different climate scenarios outputs; and iii) the uncertainties on downscaling techniques and/or bias-correction techniques.

For the UDS planning, the climate change impact is integrated throughout the update of IDF curves. Due to the current limitation of climate modelling in reproducing sub-daily/hourly weather patterns, the update of IDF cannot be easily carried out by using the outputs of climate simulation chain but it requires the implementation of a bias correction technique (Maraun, 2016; Padulano et al., 2019; Hosseinzadehtalaei et al., 2021). Padulano et al. (2025) conducted a comprehensive assessment of three of the most widely used techniques for bias correction of rainfall extremes: Quantile-Quantile Downscaling (QQD), Detrended Quantile Mapping (DQM), and Quantile Delta Mapping (QDM). The three of them have been developed under specific assumptions and objectives that make them suitable for the correction of precipitation data. From this work, it is highlighted the overall performance of DQM in reducing the model bias and preserving the climate change signal given by climate simulations.

5.5. STEP 4: Adaptation

Identifying adaptation options and limits based on local urban planning

Given the probability that the critical threshold is exceeded in the future obtained in STEP 3, it has to be determined if the system can be classified as climate-proofed or need to be improved/adapted. For that, a “tolerable” probability of exceedance, like 50, 75 or 90%, is set. The choice depends, among other things, on how conservative the decision may be. Therefore, if the probability of exceedance is higher than the tolerable value, it is necessary to establish and assess potential adaptation measures.

In general, adaptation measures can be classified as structural, like modification in the infrastructure design, or non-structural, like improving monitoring or emergency response programs. For the applications presented in the current document, the main focus is on structural measures, but it is recommended to take into account and implement also the non-structural ones. In that case, learnings from past experiences with critical events, including challenges faced during responses

and recovery from flooding events, could be highly valuable (Pfleiderer et al., 2025; Koers et al., 2024).

For the assessment of climate change adaptation measures for urban areas, decision-makers must rely on comprehensive decision-support tools to systematically prioritize options based on a range of defined criteria and sub-criteria (Barquet & Cumiskey, 2018). These tools often include methodologies such as cost-benefit analysis (CBA), cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA), and multi-criteria analysis (MCA; UNFCCC, 2011). In particular, MCA comprise different techniques and tools by which multiple objectives and decision criteria can be formally incorporated into the analysis of a problem (Dean, 2022). MCA is particularly valuable when decision-makers face complex, multidimensional challenges that cannot be fully captured through quantitative measures alone. Detailed information about these tools can be found in the The HuT Deliverable D3.4 *Quantitative and multi-criteria analyses for multi-risk Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR)*.

Once the potential adaptation measures are established, they have to be “translated” into variations of non-climate variables of the system. Then, since each adaptation measure is expected to lead to a more resilient system, it constitutes a shift in the critical threshold of the system. Therefore, a new threshold has to be calculated and integrated into the stress test space to assess the probability that it is exceeded in the future.

For UDS, structural adaptation measures may be focused on increasing the capacity of the system, either by installing larger pipes or by improving the capacity of the current infrastructure through its cleaning and restoration, or by controlling the quantity of runoff. The latter could comprise solutions such as rainwater harvesting systems, green roofs, pervious pavements, or infiltration systems (Woods-Ballard et al., 2015).

Main aspects of the application of the climate-proofing framework on the planning of an urban drainage system are summarized in Figure 5.

STEP 1 System parameters	STEP 2 Critical threshold	STEP 3 Projections	STEP 4 Adaptation
<p>Gathering relevant information for the system design/planning</p> <p><i>It should cover aspects such as:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Current drainage network - Local regulations - Hydroclimatic information - Availability of hydrological or hydraulic models of the network <p><i>Expected results:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Intensity-duration-frequency (IDF) curves for baseline conditions. - Design storm - Rainfall-runoff modeling strategy to relate rainfall intensity and peak flow - Hydraulic modeling strategy to relate runoff with pipe sizes 	<p>Identifying the climate impact-driver (CID) and its acceptable frequency of occurrence</p> <p><i>Two aspects have to be defined:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The CID to describe the climatic conditions considered problematic for the system. For example: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Precipitation intensity associated with historical flood events - The acceptable frequency of occurrence of the CID <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It may be consistent with the design storm return period <p>Elements from STEP 1 & 2 are combined on a stress test analysis to characterize the link between climate variables and system dynamics</p>	<p>Assessing the probability that the critical threshold could be significantly changed in the future</p> <p><i>It covers three main aspects:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Selection of climate change projections - Mapping projected values onto the stress test space - Estimation of probability that the critical threshold is exceeded in the future <p><i>Specific results:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Projected IDF curves <p>Climate change information is described quantitatively using a probabilistic framework based on the stress test performed on STEP 2</p>	<p>Identifying adaptation options and limits based on local urban planning</p> <p><i>Two aspects have to be defined:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “Tolerable” probability of exceedance - Potential adaptation measures <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • increasing the capacity of pipes • controlling the quantity of runoff <p><i>Additional results:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Non-structural measures: improving monitoring or emergency response programs <p>Adaptation measures have to be “translated” into variations of non-climate factors of the system and integrated into the stress test space.</p>

Figure 5. Summary of the climate-proofing framework for drainage network design

6. Application in Vilnius city, Lithuania (DEM4)

6.1. Study area

Vilnius, the capital of Lithuania, is characterized by modest elevation changes and crossed by two rivers - Neris and Vilnia. The well-preserved medieval old town of Vilnius, inscribed as a UNESCO World Heritage site in 1994, is one of the largest in Europe, covering about 3.59 square kilometers, housing landmarks of Gothic, Baroque and Renaissance architecture.

Under the climate change conditions, it is generally agreed that by the end of this century this region might face an increased risk of unprecedented intense pluvial floods (Ramanauskas et al., 2024). This poses a risk for a vulnerable and invaluable cultural heritage, which can be affected by high floodwaters, as well as the old-town residents whose properties are in the area. Therefore, a proper climate-proofing planning of the urban drainage system is required to minimize the potential climate change impacts.

6.2. Climate-proofing approach for urban drainage planning

6.2.1. System parameters

6.2.1.1. *Current drainage network*

The current old-town drainage system consists of historical brick pipes and new pipes, whose construction dates to the year 1912. It is maintained by two companies – UAB “Vilniaus vandenys” (www.vv.lt), which owns the combined network and sewage network, and UAB “Grinda” (www.grinda.lt), which maintains the separate rainwater pipes. The network of combined and separate sewage pipes is constituted of the old brick/concrete structure, and newer pipes of ceramics, PVC (Polyvinyl Chloride), and PP (Polypropylene) materials. Diameters span from 100 to 2000 mm.

Due to the sensitive nature of urban critical infrastructure information, it was not possible to obtain georeferenced data from companies responsible for urban drainage management. Therefore, online resources (<https://atviras.vplanas.lt/portal/home>) were used to get an approximate distribution and diameters of the urban drainage network in the old town (Figure 6). Then, the area draining the central part of the historical center (hashed polygon in Figure 6) was delimited based on the network distribution and the digital elevation model (DEM) obtained from the ALOS PALSAR project (<https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/data/projects/alos-palsar-rtc-project>). The area of interest has **86.6 ha** and drains into a **1200 mm** concrete pipe.

Figure 6. Approximation of Vilnius old town drainage network

6.2.1.2. Local regulations

Specifically in the Republic of Lithuania, the design of the urban drainage systems must comply with the technical regulation on construction - the STR by its acronym in Lithuanian (*Statybos techninis reglamentas*), of which the most relevant is the STR 2.07.01:2003 "*Vandentiekis ir nuotekų šalintuvas. Pastato inžinerinės sistemos. Lauko inžineriniai tinklai*" (engl. Water supply and sewage system. Building engineering systems. Outdoor engineering networks). In this legislation's annex no. 9, a detailed explanation is given on how the calculations concerning surface runoff must be carried out. It is recommended to use the rational method to estimate the surface discharge, a duration of the design storm equal to the time of concentration of the basin, and a **return period of 5 years** for streets where the overflow of the drain is unfavorable or especially unfavorable. In addition, parameters to obtain the precipitation intensity based on duration and return period are given.

6.2.1.3. Meteorological information

The meteorological information for the city of Vilnius is measured in the city's established meteorological station in Trakų Vokė, overseen by the Lithuanian hydrometeorological service. Despite its distant location from the area of interest, ~12 km, it is the only available source of sub-hourly precipitation records, necessary for the construction of IDF curves. The time series of 10-minute rainfall records covers the period 2012-2023.

IDF curves representative of the baseline period are generated with a parametric approach based on the Gumbel distribution. Since the length of the observation time series is shorter than the recommended one by the World Meteorological Organization (WMO), a simple scaling model

(Burlando & Rosso, 1996) was used to reduce the uncertainty in the estimation of the distribution parameters and guarantee coherence between IDF curves of different durations. However, it is highlighted the need to continue the monitoring of sub-hourly precipitation and update the IDF curves when more information is available. Figure 7 depicts the IDF curves for several return periods between 2 and 100 years.

Figure 7. IDF curves for Vilnius city - baseline period.

6.2.1.4. Design storm

The time of concentration of the drainage area was calculated as **~40minutes**, using the Kerby-Kirpich method (Roussel et al., 2005). Therefore, the urban drainage system in Vilnius' old town should be able to adequately handle a 5-year design storm with a duration of 40 minutes. This design storm corresponds to an intensity of **31.7 mm/h** according to the calculated IDF curves (Figure 7), or **36.6 mm/h** if the STR parameters are used.

6.2.1.5. Modeling strategies

For the current implementation, a parsimonious modeling approach is preferred, given the limited availability of information and the easy application of the following steps of the framework.

In line with local regulations, and previous studies (Cook et al., 2020; Tousi et al., 2021), the rational method is used to relate precipitation intensity (I) and peak flow (Q) following Eq. 6-1. The runoff coefficient (C) was calculated as a function of the type of land use (Di Giustino et al., 2022) based on the CORINE Land Cover categories of the Urban Atlas Land Cover/Land Use 2018 from Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (<https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/urban-atlas/urban-atlas-2018>). For the drainage area (A) of study, C takes a value of 0.76, representative of highly urbanized areas.

$$Q = C \cdot I \cdot A / 360 \left[m^3/s \right] \quad 6-1$$

For the hydraulic modeling, Manning's equation is used to calculate the discharge capacity of the given channel section (Eq. 6-2). The cross-sectional flow area (A_o) and the hydraulic ratio (R_h) are calculated as a function of the flow depth (y) on a circular pipe. A common design parameter is the relative depth of the flow with respect to the pipe diameter (y/D), also known as filling ratio. By design, the filling ratio should not be higher than 0.5 for pipes up to 200 mm, or 0.75 for larger pipes. The slope of the pipe (S_o) is estimated as 0.015 m/m using the DEM, assuming that the slope of the underground drainage pipes is not far from the surface slope. Manning's roughness coefficient (n) for concrete channels may take values between 0.011 and 0.019, depending on the canal conditions.

$$Q = A_o \cdot R_h^{2/3} \cdot S_o^{1/2} / n \quad [m^3/s] \quad 6-2$$

6.2.2. Critical threshold

6.2.2.1. Definition of the climate impact driver (CID)

Initially, to define the climatic conditions that are considered problematic for the system, i.e., the CID, two perspectives were considered. The first one consists of using the design storm intensity value, **31.7 mm/h**, since, from a design point of view, events exceeding such intensity are considered critical. The second perspective seeks to consider the real conditions of the system based on observed critical events. However, as there is not a structured database about past urban flood events and it was necessary to resort to online information. First, past flood events affecting Vilnius streets were identified from media reports, gathering approximate day and time of the event, approximate location, and approximate damage. It was possible to retrieve this information only over the past 11 years. Then, this information was crossed with meteorological records to get the precipitation intensity associated with each of the events. Finally, the case with the highest number of reports over the historical center is assumed as a critical event, i.e., the event of August 2018 with an intensity of **16.3 mm/h**.

Since the second value is lower than the design storm and indirectly represents the current capacity of the drainage infrastructure, it was selected as the CID of the system.

6.2.2.2. Acceptable frequency of occurrence of the CID

For an acceptable frequency of occurrence of critical conditions, the design storm return period is used, i.e., 5 years. This also somewhat aligns with the expectations of stakeholders and local communities.

During the VILNIUS DRR forum (<https://thehut-nexus.eu/event/vilnius-drr-forum/>), involving cultural heritage specialists, politicians, scientists, and citizens, a survey was conducted about the "*social tolerance of pluvial floods caused by intensive rainfall*". Participants were asked: "Would you feel safe if a flood with specific characteristics (depth and duration) occurred never, once every 10 years, once every 5 years, once a year, or more frequently than once a year?". In summary, all the stakeholders indicated that the historical center should be preserved the most. Most groups chose the "Never" option for any type of flood, which, although expected, cannot be considered realistic. But for flood events with moderate depth, 10-25 cm, the second most voted option was **once every 5 years**, which is in agreement with the regulation.

6.2.2.3. Stress test

To implement the stress test, it is necessary to define two aspects: on the one hand, the stressors (two relevant variables for the system) and, on the other, their range of variation. The variables selected for the stress test are the runoff coefficient (C), which represents the final percentage of rainfall volume that will reach the pipe of analysis, and the Manning’s coefficient (n), which represents the reduction in the canal capacity, either due to aging factors or the efficiency of maintenance processes. The range of variation of C goes from 0.9, for impervious areas with steep slopes, to 0.3 for green urban areas. The latter has also been associated with permeable pavements and green roofs. The variation of n , on the other hand, is based on categories representing the canal conditions, as shown in Table 1 and based on Akkuzu et al. (2008).

Table 1: Canal Conditions with respect to Manning’s Coefficient (n) for concrete

n	Canal conditions
0.011	Best (exceptional)
0.014	Good
0.016	Fair
0.019	Bad

It is worth mentioning that, given the cultural significance of the area, major engineering interventions, such as installing larger-capacity pipelines, can be extremely difficult or even impossible. Therefore, variations in pipe diameter were not considered for the stress test.

The decision space (Figure 8) is created by calculating the precipitation intensity (grey contours) associated with the peak flow that reaches a filling ratio of 0.75 in the current infrastructure, but by varying the parameters n and C . The rest of the system parameters remain static and take the values mentioned in Section 6.2.1. From these results, three intensity values are highlighted: in green the critical threshold (16.3 mm/h), in orange the design storm given by the IDF curve built with observations, and in dark-orange the design storm given by the local regulations. Additionally, the critical threshold splits the space into regions of “acceptable” (blue area) and “unacceptable” (red area) decisions.

Figure 8. Decision space built for the current drainage infrastructure of Vilnius old town

Initially, when the runoff coefficient is set as the one calculated from the land use data ($C = 0.76$), the critical threshold is reached for a pipe on “Bad” conditions, according to the Manning’s coefficient ($n = 0.019$). Therefore, it is inferred that this pair of values (visualized by black-dashed lines on the decision space) represents the current state of the system.

Additionally, both “reference” design intensities fall into the “unacceptable” region, suggesting that the current infrastructure does not meet the design requirements under the current climate. Therefore, flooding could occur with a higher frequency than the acceptable one, which is, on average, once every 5 years. It is also possible to notice that the pipe cannot withstand the design storm even if the canal is in “Best conditions”, which is actually far from reality, given the age of the pipe.

6.2.3. Projections

6.2.3.1. Climate change projections

The data used for the climate change impact assessment correspond to the results of 13 climate simulation chains for Europe under the EURO-CORDEX initiative (Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment; Jacob et al., 2014). The climate simulations used have a daily temporal resolution and a spatial resolution of 12.5 km (0.11°).

Table 2 reports the global climate model (GCM) and the regional climate model (RCM) corresponding to each simulation chain.

Table 2: Climate simulation chains - EURO-CORDEX – used for Vilnius analysis

ID	GCM	RCM
1	CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5	CNRM-ALADIN63
2	CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5	KNMI-RACMO22E
3	ICHEC-EC-EARTH	CLMcom-CCLM4-8-17
4	ICHEC-EC-EARTH	KNMI-RACMO22E
5	ICHEC-EC-EARTH	SMHI-RCA4
6	ICHEC-EC-EARTH	DMI-HIRHAM5
7	MOHC-HadGEM2-ES	SMHI-RCA4
8	MOHC-HadGEM2-ES	DMI-HIRHAM5
9	MOHC-HadGEM2-ES	KNMI-RACMO22E
10	MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR	MPI-CSC-REMO2009
11	MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR	SMHI-RCA4
12	NCC-NorESM1-M	GERICS-REMO2015
13	NCC-NorESM1-M	SMHI-RCA4

Furthermore, the three concentration scenarios known as RCP (Representative Concentration Pathway; Meinshausen et al., 2011) are used, adopted as a reference for the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change of the United Nations (IPCC, 2014). The three scenarios “force” the models through the variation of the concentration of the shares of climate-altering gases. In particular:

- **RCP2.6:** describes an “optimistic” scenario, assumes “aggressive” mitigation strategies for which emissions begin to decline in 2020 and reach zero by 2100.
- **RCP4.5:** is an intermediate scenario in which it is assumed that the implementation of some initiatives to control emissions. In the RCP4.5, emissions peak around 2040 and then reach half the 2050 levels in 2100.
- **RCP8.5:** is a “worst case scenario” where emissions continue to rise throughout the 21st century. The RCP 8.5 is characterized by the occurrence of intensive consumption of fossil fuels and the failure to adopt any mitigation policy.

The numerical suffix represents the expected increase in radiative forcing in 2100 compared to pre-industrial levels.

The analysis is made for the 30-yrs period centered around 2070 with respect to a historical reference period between 1981 and 2010. The selection of a thirty-year period according to the WMO guidelines allows to adequately take into account interannual variations while reducing, at the same time, the probability that statistically significant trends may arise in the sample that could undermine the hypothesis of sample homogeneity.

6.2.3.2. Updating IDF curves under climate change scenarios

Simulated precipitation data was adjusted with the Detrended Quantile Mapping (DQM, Bürger et al., 2013; Cannon et al., 2015) technique in order to minimize the bias with respect to the historical IDF curves (Figure 7) and preserve most of the climate signal given by the climate models (Padulano et al., 2025). Figure 9 presents projected IDF curves for a return period of 5 years, dashed-thick lines indicate the median value for each RCP and the filled area cover between the 10th and 90th percentiles of model projections.

Figure 9. Projected IDF curves for Vilnius city - 2070 period.

6.2.3.3. Probability of exceedance of problematic conditions in the future

To assess the probability of exceedance of problematic conditions in the future, projected design storm intensity is integrated into the decision space. Figure 10 shows the same space of Figure 8 but it is highlighted the range of projected values, between the lowest intensity (26.7 mm/h) and the maximum one (49.2 mm/h). Besides, projections from individual models are mapped onto the current system axes (dashed lines).

It is evident that all climate projections fall into the “unacceptable” region, meaning a 100% probability of exceeding the critical threshold of the system by 2070. Therefore, it is clear that the system needs to be improved or adapted to handle future extreme precipitation events. Result that was expected since the “reference” values fall also into the unacceptable region.

Figure 10. Projected design storm intensities mapped onto the decision space

6.2.4. Adaptation

In the adaptation process, a “tolerable” probability of exceedance of 50% is assumed. It means, on one hand that the system cannot be considered as climate-proofed, since the current probability of exceedance is 100%, and on the other hand, that adaptation measures should allow to have a new critical threshold close to the median of the climate projections (**36.2 mm/h**).

This new threshold can be reached by many combinations of C and n . For example, Figure 11 shows a proposed solution where the reduction in the value of both stressors is required. First, the capacity of the pipe needs to be improved by **26%** changing from Bad to Good canal conditions. Second, the runoff retention should be increased by **40%** so the runoff coefficient changes from 0.76 to 0.46. For the latter aspect, it cannot be considered only the increase of green areas. Otherwise, it would require that 90% of areas classified as Continuous urban fabric (S.L. : > 80%) and roads to be modified for green roof and permeable pavement ($C = 0.3$) as shown in Figure 12.

Figure 11. Decision space considering adaptation measures

Figure 12. Required changes on land cover/land use to pass from a runoff coefficient of 0.76 (left) to 0.46 (right).

The specific adaptation measures have to be identified, analyzed, and designed based on local physical characteristics, adaptation capacity, and, if it is possible, community needs.

7. Application in Naples, Italy (DEM3)

7.1. Study area

The area chosen for this application is located in the western part of the city of Naples, Italy. It is part of the largest drainage basin in Western Naples, Arena S. Antonio. This drainage basin is one of the most complex ones within the Naples drainage system, having a sewer system which is not known in detail (Del Giudice and Padulano, 2016). The system has suffered surcharge problems in recent years because of a combination of an uncontrolled urbanization of the area, a lack of effective maintenance, and an increasing number of high-intensity rainfall events due to climate change (Del Giudice and Padulano, 2016).

7.2. Climate-proofing approach for urban drainage planning

7.2.1. System parameters

7.2.1.1. Current drainage network

The selected subbasin of Arena S. Antonio basin, hereinafter referred to as Via Epomeo, partially covers the neighborhood of Soccavo and a small area of Arenella (Figure 13). It has a total area of **143 ha**; it has 60% urbanized area and 40% area corresponding to pastures and forests. The latter is located at the highest part of the basin. The sewer starts from 124 m.a.s.l. and the terminal collector, located over Via Epomeo, has an average altitude of 87 m.a.s.l. The main sewer was built on concrete and it has a rectangular cross-section with a **width of 150 cm** and a **height of 200 cm**.

Figure 13. Approximation of Via Epomeo drainage network

7.2.1.2. Local regulations

Specifically in the European area, D.P.C.M of March 4th 1996 states that “... for the purposes of rainwater drainage and sewerage networks must be sized and managed in such a way as to ensure that backflow phenomena do not affect the street level or the discharge of sewage more frequently than **once every five years** for each individual network”. Therefore, **5 years** is taken as the return period for the design storm of the study area.

Additionally, the VAPI (Flood Evaluation) project, sponsored by the Italian National Research Council (CNR–GNDCI), is the Italian initiative for regional frequency analysis of extreme rainfall and flood data (Rossi & Villani, 1994), providing guidelines for design, planning, and management purposes throughout the Italian territory. Specifically with regards to extreme precipitation, the District of Naples, including 44 rain gauges with sub-daily observations, provides regional IDF curves that rely on the storm index method; the storm index method is particularly used to interpret extreme precipitation values because it ensures rainfall consistency, namely, it preserves the increasing dependence of precipitation depth on both duration and return period (Padulano et. al., 2019).

According to the storm index method, the rainfall depth of an extreme precipitation event with return period T and rainfall duration d can be estimated as the product of a scale parameter (μ) only depending on duration, and a frequency parameter or “growth factor” (k_T) only depending on the return period:

$$h_T(d) = \mu(d) \cdot k_T [mm] \quad 7-1$$

Padulano et. al. (2019) calibrated depth-duration-frequency (DDF) curves for Napoli, using information at the *Napoli Servizio Idrografico* (NSI) rain gauge in the period 1971–2000. The calibration of the DDF curves relies on the separate estimation of an equation for mean values μ and of a probability distribution for growth factors k_T . In their case, a generalized extreme value (GEV) probability distribution was assumed. However, it has been noted that GEV can lead to incoherent results, especially when climate model projections are involved. Therefore, in the present application, a transformation of the GEV parameters from Padulano et. al. (2019) into parameters of a Gumbel distribution was performed in order to avoid potential inconsistencies.

7.2.1.3. Meteorological information

For the Italian territory, the VAPI project allows us to have information about extreme precipitation required for the design of urban drainage. However, as mentioned in the current framework description, it is highly recommended to update IDF curves when there are rainfall records available. For the current analysis, it was possible to obtain information at the Napoli Camaldoli rain gauge through the *Centro Funzionale Multirischi della Protezione Civile Regione Campania* web portal. The rain gauge is located in the north-eastern border of the Via Epomeo basin (see Figure 13), the rainfall records have a temporal resolution of 10-minute and cover the period 2001-2024.

The storm index method was implemented using Gumbel parameters mentioned previously to describe the growth factors and μ values calibrated using Napoli Camaldoli information. In this way, it was possible to generate IDF curves representative of the baseline period and coherent with the Italian regulation. Figure 14 depicts the IDF curves for several return periods between 2 and 100 years.

Figure 14. IDF curves for Napoli Camaldoli - baseline period.

7.2.1.4. Design storm

The time of concentration of the drainage area was calculated as **~70minutes**, using the Kerby-Kirpich method. Therefore, the urban drainage system in Via Epomeo should be able to adequately handle a 5-year design storm with a duration of 70 minutes, corresponding to an intensity of **43.6 mm/h** according to the updated IDF curves (Figure 14).

7.2.1.5. Modeling strategies

Considering the lack of detailed information about the drainage system, the same modeling strategy followed for Vilnius is implemented here (see Section 6.2.1.5), using a runoff coefficient (C) of 0.51, calculated with the CORINE Land Cover categories, and the slope of the pipe (S_o) is estimated as 0.006 m/m using the digital elevation model.

7.2.2. Critical threshold

7.2.2.1. Definition of the climate impact driver (CID)

In the same way as in the case of DEM4 climatic conditions that are considered problematic for the system were identified based on recent flood events reported in newspapers (online). First, dates and approximate location of past flood events affecting western Napoli were identified from media reports. This information is only available for the past 15 years and has not been extended backward using additional sources, so the information is consistent with the current state of the system. Then, the identified dates were crossed with meteorological records from Napoli Camaldoli to get the precipitation intensity associated with each of the events. Finally, three events were identified as potential critical events due to their location and recorded intensity in 70 minutes: November 6th 2011 (**29.3 mm/h**), September 23rd 2019 (**30.5 mm/h**), and November 17th 2020 (**31.5 mm/h**).

7.2.2.2. *Acceptable frequency of occurrence of the CID*

For the acceptable frequency of occurrence of critical conditions, the design storm return period is used, i.e., 5 years. For the implementation of the climate-proofing framework in Napoli, there was no participatory discussion. However, for future replications on real-case analysis, it is highly recommended to involve stakeholders and communities that can be impacted by potential infrastructure changes.

7.2.2.3. *Stress test*

The stress test was made using three variables (non-climate stressors) so it was possible to make a clear description and assessment of the current infrastructure and also an analysis of potential adaptation measures.

The variables selected for the stress test are the runoff coefficient (C), which represents the final percentage of rainfall volume that will reach the pipe of analysis, the Manning's coefficient (n), which represents the reduction in the canal capacity, either due to aging factors or the efficiency of maintenance processes, and pipe dimensions (Base x Height) which, despite representing a strong engineering intervention, can still be considered as a possibility in the case of Naples.

The used range of variation of C goes from 0.7 to 0.3, while the variation of n is consistent with the variation presented for Vilnius, and it is based on categories representing the canal conditions, as shown in Table 1. The variation on pipe dimensions was taken from the Cazan catalogue of rectangular reinforced pipes (<https://canzian.it/wp-content/uploads/2016/03/Tubo-rettangolare-armato-uso-orizzontale.pdf>).

The first decision space, shown in Figure 15, was generated to describe and assess the current infrastructure. Therefore, it was not considered a change in pipe dimensions. The processes of generating the space consist of obtaining for each pair of n and C the precipitation intensity associated with a peak flow that fills a pipe, with the same dimensions and slope as the current infrastructure, up to a filling ratio of 0.75 (design parameter). The calculations were made based on the modeling strategy described previously.

The calculated intensity is shown with grey contours and five specific values are highlighted: in orange is the storm design, in light-blue, purple and magenta are the critical events, and in green is the intensity associated with the pair of $n = 0.019$ and $C = 0.51$ (values indicated with dashed lines). In this case, to improve the visualization, background colors for "acceptable" and "unacceptable" areas were not included.

Initially, it should be noted that critical events have a magnitude much lower than the design storm, suggesting that the system is reaching surcharge conditions with precipitation events smaller than the expected ones. Then, when these values are put in context against the capacity of the pipe (Manning's coefficient) and using the current runoff coefficient, it is found that critical events are associated with a state of the canal close to "Bad conditions". Finally, the difference between the intensity related to Bad conditions and the design storm evidence a potential need for improvement.

Figure 15. Decision space built for the current drainage infrastructure of Via Epomeo

Finally, Figure 16 shows the decision spaces that are going to be contrasted against climate projections. Spaces are split into regions of “acceptable” (blue area) and “unacceptable” (red area) decisions based on the critical intensity value of **28.5 mm/h** (green contour). In particular, to generate the space with variations in pipe dimensions “Good” conditions of the canal were assumed. This decision is based on the fact that there is no added value in comparing projected design storms against different pipes with Bad conditions. “Good” conditions of the canal is a standard assumption during the design process. From this, it can be noticed that the current critical intensity (i_{crit}) is close to the associated capacity of a pipe of 1.5 x 1.5 m².

Figure 16. Decision spaces using as stressors the runoff coefficient and Manning's coefficient (left) or pipe dimensions (right)

7.2.3. Projections

7.2.3.1. Climate change projections

The data used for the climate change impact assessment correspond to the results of 14 climate simulation chains for Europe under the EURO-CORDEX initiative (Jacob et al., 2014). It includes the 13 model chains listed in

Table 2 plus the model MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR_MPI-CSC-REMO2009_r2i1p1, to ensure consistency with the selection conducted by the National Plan for Adaptation to Climate Change ([PNACC - Piano Nazionale di Adattamento ai Cambiamenti Climatici - Dicembre 2022, Ministro dell'ambiente e della sicurezza energetica](#)).

As in the implementation for Vilnius, three climate change scenarios were considered: RCP2.6, RCP4.5, and RCP8.5, the period of references is considered between 1981 and 2010, and the future period of interest consists of 30 years centered in 2070.

7.2.3.2. Updating IDF curves under climate change scenarios

Simulated precipitation data were adjusted with the DQM technique (Bürger et al., 2013, Cannon et al., 2015) in order to minimize the bias with respect to the historical IDF curves (Figure 14) and preserve most of the climate signal given by the climate models (Padulano et al., 2025). Figure 17 presents projected IDF curves for a return period of 5 years, dashed-thick lines indicate the median value for each RCP and the filled area covers between the 10th and 90th percentiles of model projections. Here, it is evident that most of the projections indicate a potential increase in the intensity of extreme precipitation of different durations. The increase is particularly large for durations lower than 3 hours, suggesting a high impact for urban areas with a short time of concentration.

Figure 17. Projected IDF curves for Via Epomeo - 2070 period.

7.2.3.3. Probability of exceedance of problematic conditions in the future

To assess the probability of exceedance of problematic conditions in the future, projected design storm intensity is included in the decision spaces. Figure 18 shows the same spaces as in Figure 16, but projections from individual models are mapped onto the current system axes (dashed lines), and the range of projected values is highlighted, between the lowest intensity (35 mm/h) and the maximum one (74.1 mm/h). The range of almost 39 mm/h shows a large uncertainty in future changes of extreme precipitation over the study area.

From these results, one can notice that all climate projections fall into the “unacceptable” region, meaning that all models and scenarios project an exceedance of the critical threshold of the system by 2070. Therefore, it is suggested that the system needs to be improved or adapted to handle future extreme precipitation events.

Figure 18. Projected design storm intensities mapped onto the decision spaces of Via Epomeo

7.2.4. Adaptation

Assuming a “tolerable” probability of exceedance of 50%, the adaptation measures aim to improve the system in a way that it is able to handle a storm intensity of **56.2 mm/h** with a duration of **70 minutes** which is associated to a **return period of 5 years**. These conditions are considered the new critical threshold of the system.

There are two proposed solutions based on the three system variables considered in the analysis (Figure 19). On one hand, it is required to improve the capacity of the current infrastructure in a way that it reaches a capacity close to the design values (Good capacity). This change should be accompanied by an increase in the area's runoff retention, so the runoff coefficient changes from 0.51 to 0.35. On the other hand, considering the possibility of increasing the dimensions of the collector, one solution could be an increase of 0.5 m in the height of the pipe with an additional change of the runoff coefficient from 0.51 to 0.46. However, these are just two potential adaptation options, and, as mentioned before, final measures design should be based on the local context.

Figure 19. Decision spaces considering potential adaptation measures – Via Epomeo

8. Conclusions

These Guidelines on climate-proofing planning were developed as part of the activities conducted within Task 3.1 “Enablers and barriers to multi-hazard/systemic risk reduction”. They provide a framework that is expected to assist in identifying risks associated with climate change and the potential need to adapt or improve current and future infrastructure. The framework was developed under a bottom-up approach that prioritizes the understanding of the system and its relationship with the climate. Particular attention was given to urban drainage systems, due to their essential role in the proper functioning of cities. However, the framework was designed so that it can be easily replicated for different systems or infrastructures.

The final part of the document is dedicated to the application of the framework in two different cities in Europe. In both cases, a simplified modeling strategy was selected, not only due to the lack of detailed information about the system, but also due to its complexity. However, it is important to mention that the framework is flexible and it allows the use of more complex models, but it has to be kept in mind that they can be computationally expensive, especially during the stress test implementation.

Finally, three general aspects are worth highlighting for the climate-proofing planning process:

1. **Consider the relevance of the local context in the planning process** for:
 - a. the identification of climate conditions that can be considered critical, using for example inspections of the current infrastructure to identify the actual conditions, degradation, and potential variations on its functionality; using historical events that have been reported as critical either in the news or by the community.
 - b. the definition and selection of potential adaptation measures (as well as limits in the adaptation capacity) using tools such as multi-criteria analysis methods.
2. **Appropriated use of climate change projections.** It is important to take into account:
 - a. the selection of a model ensemble that is representative of climate change uncertainties to improve the robustness of the results. The ensemble should include outputs of different modeling centers and under different future scenarios, unless there is a particular interest in the impacts of a specific scenario.
 - b. the reduction of the inherent climate modeling bias. The correction of model errors or bias may imply the use of the most straightforward method known as the ‘perturbation method’ or ‘delta-change’ approach, where differences between the historical and future simulations are applied to baseline observations through a simple additive or multiplicative operation (Croce et. al., 2019); or implementing more sophisticated statistical techniques based on the correction of the entire probabilistic distribution, such as those discussed in Padulano et. al. (2025). The chosen method depends on the specific project and climate variables involved in the design.
3. **Involving stakeholders through the planning process contributes to a better perception of the project and an easier final implementation.** Decisions regarding “unacceptable” performance of the system, key parameters considered in the stress test, potential adaptation measures, are just some aspects that, if defined jointly with stakeholders, can have greater meaning and precision. Besides, neglecting stakeholders can result in assessments that lack legitimacy in the eyes of the community, politicians and other decision makers.

9. References

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